

MODERN TRANSLATION STRATEGIES

Annotation: This article defines the content of the concept of "translation strategy", briefly describes its main components and identifies the main principles that a translator should be guided by when choosing a translation strategy.

Keywords: translation strategy, translation quality, written translation, stages of written translation, translation models .

Modern translation studies are at the stage of transition from the comparative-structural type of ontology to the activity type through self-reflection , which is expressed in the turning of scientific knowledge on itself with the involvement of philosophical and methodological knowledge. Self-reflection allows us to reconsider the main categories and concepts of translation studies on other grounds and, thus, to find their place in a broader context - the context of humanitarian knowledge. One of the main concepts of substitutive -transformational translation studies , which requires deep study in the aspect of philosophical and methodological knowledge, is the concept of a translation strategy for a scientific text.

The concept of strategy in substitutive -transformational translation studies was used as an integral part of translation competence and meant the process of making a translation decision at individual levels of the language. The strategy was defined as the development of a program of translation actions and the implementation of this program, namely the performance of rational operations, expressed in the choice of literal, free, literal, exact types of translation, following a number of principles, for example, the principle of identifying successive sections of text in IT and their consecutive translation. This view of the strategy is due to the linguistic concepts that formed the basis of translation studies as a science.

Historically, translation studies were formed under the influence of the comparative-historical and structuralist trends in linguistics. Within the framework of comparative historical linguistics, characterized by the desire to identify family ties and correspondences between languages by comparing phonemes, roots, individual words, grammatical forms, a

typology of languages was created, indicating the existence of certain patterns between languages. The principle of comparison as the identification of general and particular in the lexico-grammatical aspect of the language and the principle of historicism as the evolution of language forms that require the search for correspondences in a certain historical section had a decisive influence on the theory of translation, since when comparing languages, word-for-word interlinear or literal translation was used in the form of linguistic analysis. Representatives of the structuralist trend (F. de Saussure, A. Seche, C. Bally, L. Elmslev, W. Brendahl, H.J. Uldall and others) studied language as an immanent system that has its own order and relationships, characterized by the dominance of form, not substances. The central concepts were the concepts of structure as a way of existence and description of the language, meaning as the content of the word in relation to the designated object and significance as the relationship (syntagmatic and / or paradigmatic) of the word to other words in the language system. Substitutive -transformational translation studies, having originated within structuralism, borrowed from it a way of operating with linguistic units in the form of an analysis of their structure and content, as well as a search for an invariant limited by the limit of variation of a linguistic sign.

A distinctive feature of the substitutive -transformational theory of translation is the use of a phenomenological explanation, which is expressed in subsuming the fact of translation under an empirical law, i.e. the observed is explained through the observed, namely through words, phrases, syntactic constructions, etc.

One of the main problems of linguo-cognitive translation studies is the choice of the method of translation of the original knowledge, which determines the translation strategy.

The concept of strategy (Greek *strategia*) is borrowed by modern science from the art of military affairs, in which strategy was defined as the doctrine of the best location and use of military forces to achieve the goal. In military affairs, strategy was implemented through tactics, directing the activities of the subjects of strategy, determining strategic behavior, in particular, planning as a choice of action based on optimality criteria. The interpretation of strategy and tactics in philosophy seems to us to be the most relevant to the requirements of modern translation studies, which recognizes the importance of the

analytical thinking of the translating person in the processes of understanding and interpreting the source text. Thanks to analytical thinking, the translator is able to reconstruct the "procedure" embedded in the source text and correlated with the typological dominant of the source text. The opinion of P.Kh. Torop, who believed that the translation of the source text is due to the translation dominant, expressed in the transfer of the typological parameter of the translated text. In the aspect of translation of a scientific text, this kind of dominant can be considered conceptualization as a logical and semantic design of scientific knowledge. So, when translating a scientific text, the translator forms and operates with special constructions, which are means of mental work that open access to scientific knowledge. Such constructions in scientific knowledge are logical relations (propositions), the totality of which makes it possible to present an object as an integral phenomenon.

The methodology states that the formation of a strategy is possible on the basis of a person's idea of the whole, on the basis of which these ideas will be combined and carried out in accordance with a certain technique. G.P. Shchedrovitsky notes that "the concept of strategy in general arises only after we get the opportunity to achieve some goal, or solve some problem in different ways and ways." Consequently, the development of a strategy is the result of the mental and practical activity of an individual, which involves the use of both theoretical and practical data.

The purpose of applying the strategy of translation of a scientific text is to create a successful translation of a scientific text that expresses the author's model of knowledge.

The choice of a scientific text translation strategy is determined by both objective and subjective factors. The former include the type of text, the type of communication, and the type of cognition. The second type of factors includes the translator's professional competence, which implies, in addition to knowing a foreign language, the ability to interpret and understand the original scientific text, as well as the ability to formalize the understood special knowledge in accordance with the norms of the target language.

Logical relations, acting as a way of connecting the components of the model, are an "international substance" that repeats the course of the author's thought. The linguistic embodiment of logical relations occurs on the basis of analogy, which allows "to give

similar conceptual structures similar forms in the linguistic embodiment”, as a result of which logical relations in a scientific text are explicit in nature and determine its typological parameter - logic.

Scientific communication is conditioned by a number of factors: the addresser, the addressee, the specifics of their interaction, the nature of the message, the features of the code, etc. The translation of a scientific text as a type of scientific communication includes the stages of intrapersonal (“I” -“I”) and interpersonal (“I”-“OH ”) communications. At the first stage (intrapersonal communication), the translator understands new scientific knowledge expressed in IT. The result of understanding is the construction by the translator of the original author's model of knowledge. Achieving understanding is possible by interpreting a scientific text, i.e. comprehension of linguistic and cognitive units in order to recreate a holistic model of author's knowledge based on the logical relations of IT. The purpose of the translation of a scientific text in the aspect of communication is to gradually move the translator from the position of an indirect communicator to the position of a direct communicator . To achieve this goal, the translator solves the following tasks: he masters special knowledge and translates it into the PT. The solution of these problems is achieved through the adaptation and socialization of the translator in scientific translation.

Adaptation is the identification of the logic of the original scientific text, which allows you to recreate a holistic model of the author's knowledge. In scientific translation, the identification of the logic of constructing the author's concept is expressed in the conceptual subordination of the translator to the author, i.e. in following a resistive translation strategy. Socialization is manifested in the creation by the translator of a successful translation text, i.e. a type of foreign language text that is capable of objectifying new scientific knowledge created in a different language environment. One of the prerequisites for the objectification of new scientific knowledge in a different language environment is the conceptualization of the source text recreated by the translator on the basis of logical relations. Successfully recreated conceptualization allows the recipients of the translated text to understand the original author's concept.

The translator of a scientific text is faced with the task of accurately translating the model of scientific knowledge based on logical relations, since they are a component of the cognitive assimilation mechanism inherent in all people, and also ensure the understanding of new scientific knowledge by a foreign language recipient. Ignoring the nature of scientific knowledge and the scientific type of text can lead to an incorrect translation by the translator of the logical connections of the author's model of knowledge.

Misunderstanding of a scientific text is the result of an incorrect interpretation of the original special knowledge by the translator. The interpretation of a scientific text is the comprehension of linguistic units and concepts in order to recreate the author's model of knowledge based on the principle that sets the original type of text itself, its logic. The interpretation of a scientific text consists in identifying language units (basic words, explicatives and associatives) and the relationship between them. The goal of interpreting a scientific text is to understand a special text based on an individual model of knowledge. Unlike the interpretation of a literary text, which implies a plurality of interpretations due to the fact that this type of text is culturally determined and is intended for a “wide” audience, the interpretation of a scientific text is limited by the logic of certain scientific knowledge and scientific knowledge in general. The logic of scientific knowledge is manifested in the ordering and objectification of the results of scientific knowledge. As a result, the interpretation of a scientific text is based on the principle of moving from old knowledge to new, from “basic” to “constructed”. Based on this principle, the translator arranges and constructs the original special knowledge.

Thus, a feature of the translation strategy of a scientific text, due to objective and subjective factors, is the translator's re-creation of the original knowledge model embedded in IT, based on the interpretation and understanding of the features of the conceptualization of scientific knowledge in IT.

LITERATURE:

1. Schweitzer A.D. Translation theory. Status, problems, aspects. M., 2018.
2. Komissarov V.N. Communicative Problems of Translation: Modern Paradigms // Translation and Communication. M., 2017.

3. Furs J.R. Linguistic analysis and translation // Questions of the theory of translation in foreign linguistics: Sat. Art. M., 2018.

4. Alekseeva L.M. Specificity of scientific translation: textbook for a special course. Perm, 2012.